

muFHR1

Emr1

Cx3cr1

pha

merged

muFHR1 Emr1 Cx3cr1 pha merged

bleeding

muFHR1

Emr1

Iba1

pha

merged

merged

muFHR1

Emr1

Iba1

pha

Raw Data_IHC_Animal Models

Link to Figure: <https://omero.charite.de/figure/file/49236/>

Figure contains the following images:

mouse n70.lif [scar2_zoom] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923229>

mouse n89.lif [scar 1 FHRE- Iba+ zoom] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923490>

mouse n91.lif [scar 1 zoom] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923507>

mouse n95.lif [scar 1 zoom] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923547>

mouse n38.lif [scar 1 FHRE EMR1 pha] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-516971>

mouse n92.lif [scar 1 bleeding] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923527>

mouse n63.lif [scar1] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923175>

mouse n12.lif [FHRE pha EMR1 GFP x40 stressed cells_000] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-510250>

mouse n18.lif [FHRE pha EMR1 EGF x40] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-510373>

mouse n11.lif [FHRE.AF405_EMR1.AF647_pha] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-510360>

mouse n16.lif [FHRE pha EMR1 EGFP x40] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-510369>

mouse n20.lif [FHRE pha EGFP EMR1 x20 periphery_20] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-510384>

mouse n101.lif [RPE cells FHRE] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923475>

mouse n17.lif [FHRE pha EMR1 EGF] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-510371>

mouse n19.lif [FHRE pha EGRP EMR1 x20] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-510375>

mouse n15.lif <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-510367>

mouse n82.lif [Iba1 FHRE+ cells] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923458>

m_506.lif [L_Scar1_x40] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-921854>

m_512 (2).lif [L_Scar1_x40] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-921907>

m_513.lif [L scar 3 zoom FHRE-Iba1] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-921920>

m_517.lif [scar 2] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923533>

m525.lif [scar 2 x40] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-921957>

546 mouse_new.lif [R scar 1 x20 30 steps] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-922059>

549 mouse.lif [R scar2 pha FHRE zoom] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-922093>

mouse n88.lif [R scar 1 FHRE- Iba1 zoom] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923561>

72 mouse.lif [scar 2 x40] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-921764>

mouse n86.lif [scar 1 FHRE- Iba1+] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923520>

550 mouse.lif [R scar 1 zoom] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-922105>

mouse n87.lif [R scar 1-2 FHRE- Iba1+] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-923542>

545 mouse_new.lif [R scar 1 x20] <https://omero.charite.de/webclient/?show=image-922032>

Scalebars:

Scalebar Lengths: 50 μm